

MEDICAL SCIENCES

UDC: 616.33-006.6

STOMACH CANCER: CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND THEIR SOLUTIONS

A. Khozhayev,

Professor of the Department of Oncology named after S.N. Nugmanov,
Asfendiyarov Kazakh National Medical University, Almaty, Kazakhstan

A. Kukhareva,

Deputy Director Clinical Services,
Multidisciplinary «Center of Oncology and Surgery»,
East Kazakhstan region, Ust-Kamenogorsk, Kazakhstan

R. Abdurassulov,

Head of the Oncology Polyclinic of the Oncological Center,
Regional Clinical Hospital, Turkestan Region, Kazakhstan

A. Naimassov,

Surgeon Oncologist,
Konaev Multidisciplinary City Hospital, Konaev, Kazakhstan

Z. Turlybek,

Oncologist-chemotherapist,
Almaty Oncology Center, Almaty, Kazakhstan

A. Abilkassymova

Oncologist,
Balkhash Central District Hospital, Almaty region, Kazakhstan
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11550469>

Abstract

This scientific and analytical work presents modern global and local-regional data on incidence, mortality, lethality and five-year survival rate of such a common oncological pathology as stomach cancer. The issues related to risk factors, etiopathogenesis, peculiarities of spread and clinical manifestations, as well as measures for the prevention of this formidable disease are covered in detail. The epidemiological characteristics of this nosological form of malignant neoplasms in our republic in the context of the regions of the country are given.

Keywords: oncology, stomach cancer, risk factors, etiopathogenesis, epidemiology, incidence, mortality, lethality, five-year survival rate, prevention, prognosis.

Stomach cancer (SC) is a multifactorial disease. Despite a decline in incidence and mortality during the last decades, SC is one of the main health challenges worldwide. According to the GLOBOCAN 2020 estimates, SC caused approximately 800000 deaths (accounting for 7.7% of all cancer deaths), and ranks as the fourth leading cause of cancer deaths in both genders combined. About 1.1 million new cases of SC were diagnosed in 2020 (accounting for 5.6% of all cancer cases). About 75% of all new cases and all deaths from SC are reported in Asia. SC is one of the most lethal malignant tumors, with a five-year survival rate of around 20%. There are some well-established risk factors for SC: *Helicobacter pylori* infection, dietary factors, tobacco, obesity, and radiation. To date, the most important way of preventing SC is reduced exposure to risk factors, as well as screening and early detection. Further research on risk factors can help identify various opportunities for more effective prevention. Screening programs for SC have been implemented in a few countries, either as a national or opportunistic screening of high-risk individuals only. Generally, due to its high aggressiveness and heterogeneity, SC still remains a severe global health problem [1].

No pathognomonic symptoms of SC have been es-

tablished. Complaints may correspond to manifestations of various stomach diseases (chronic gastritis, gastric ulcer, etc.): pain in the epigastric region; dysphagia; nausea; vomiting (including “coffee grounds”); loss of appetite; weight loss.

During physical examination: 1) the position of the patient in late stages of SC, often forced with severe adynamia; 2) when examining the face, a decrease in the shine and liveliness of the eyes may occur; 3) pallor of the skin may be an indication of gastrointestinal bleeding; the skin of patients with late stages of SC acquires a waxy or earthy tint; in some cases, with the development of metastases in the sympathetic nodes of the abdominal cavity, pronounced diffuse hyperpigmentation of the skin can be observed; in advanced stages of SC, dry skin and decreased skin turgor are also noted; 4) severe weight loss, reaching the degree of cachexia, occurs in cancer of the distal stomach; in such cases, patients also develop protein-free edema; in the late stages, in the supraclavicular region on the left between the legs of the sternocleidomastoid muscle, it is sometimes possible to identify a dense lymph node with an uneven surface, not fused to the adjacent skin (Virchow’s metastasis); 5) when examining the oral cavity, patients with SC may experience foul odor from the

mouth - a sign of the disintegration of a malignant tumor of the stomach; 6) bulging of the abdominal wall in the epigastric region is observed in advanced forms of SC; with sudden weight loss, in some cases it is possible to visually determine the contours of the stomach, its lesser and greater curvature; 7) with the development of tumor stenosis of the pylorus, in some patients periodic wave-like movements are detected, lifting the anterior abdominal wall in limited areas, which become more distinct after preliminary light tapping of the abdominal wall in the epigastric region [2].

When palpating the anterior abdominal wall, stomach tumors are clearly palpable in cases where they are located predominantly in the distal parts of the stomach (antral, pyloric) and reach several centimeters in diameter. With percussion, you can clarify the position of the lower border of the stomach and detect changes in Traube's space (for cancer of the subcardial part of the stomach).

Laboratory studies include: 1) cytological examination (increase in cell size up to giant, change in the shape and number of intracellular elements, increase in the size of the nucleus, its contours, different degrees of maturity of the nucleus and other cell elements, changes in the number and shape of nucleoli); 2) histological examination (large polygonal or spine-shaped cells with well-defined cytoplasm, round nuclei with clear nucleoli, with the presence of mitoses, cells are located in the form of cells and strands with or without the formation of keratin, the presence of tumor emboli in the vessels, the severity of lymphocytic-plasmacytic infiltration, mitotic activity tumor cells): HER-2, Cytokeratin 7, Cytokeratin 8/18, CD45; 3) comprehensive genomic profiling in patients with a severe clinical course, aggressive tumors, with a high risk of progression, and lack of effect from traditional methods of antitumor treatment.

Instrumental research methods include: 1) fibroesophagogastroduodenoscopy (allows you to see the mucosal defect, determine its size and nature, take a piece of tissue for histological examination); 2) fluoroscopic examination of the esophagus with contrast, fluoroscopic examination of the stomach with contrast (double contrast) – allows you to determine the extent and extent of the stomach tumor, as well as determine the tactics of surgical intervention; 3) comprehensive ultrasound diagnostics (liver, gallbladder, pancreas, spleen, kidneys, supraclavicular lymph nodes) – echoic presence of enlarged lymph nodes of the abdominal cavity and retroperitoneal space, the presence of metastases in the abdominal cavity, as well as germination of SC into adjacent structures; 4) computed tomography of the abdominal organs and retroperitoneal space (more clear visualization of the presence of enlarged lymph nodes of the abdominal cavity and retroperitoneal space, the presence of metastases in the abdominal cavity, as well as the germination of a malignant neoplasm of the stomach into neighboring structures); 5) morphological examination is the main method of differential diagnosis of SC with other diseases; at the same time, the detection of malignant cells in a biopsy specimen clearly indicates esophageal cancer, although

the absence of signs of a tumor in a single sample obtained does not exclude this disease; only with repeated negative results along with dynamic observation can the pathological process be considered benign [2].

Tamura T. et al. [3], in their study, examined in detail the effects of alcohol on the development of SC, as the authors note, the association between alcohol intake and SC risk remains controversial. Our colleagues undertook a pooled analysis of data from six large-scale Japanese cohort studies with 256 478 participants on this topic. Alcohol intake as ethanol was estimated using a validated questionnaire. The participants were followed for incidence of SC. Researchers calculated study-specific hazard ratios (HRs) and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) for SC according to alcohol intake using a Cox regression model. Summary HRs were estimated by pooling the study-specific HRs using a random-effects model. During 4 265 551 person-years of follow-up, 8586 SC cases were identified. In men, the multivariate-adjusted HRs (95% CIs) of SC were 1.00 (0.87-1.15) for occasional drinkers, and 1.00 (0.91-1.11) for <23 g/d, 1.09 (1.01-1.18) for 23 to <46 g/d, 1.18 (1.09-1.29) for 46 to <69 g/d, 1.21 (1.05-1.39) for 69 to <92 g/d, and 1.29 (1.11-1.51) for ≥ 92 g/d ethanol in regular drinkers compared with nondrinkers. In women, the multivariate-adjusted HRs were 0.93 (0.80-1.08) for occasional drinkers, and 0.85 (0.74-0.99) for <23 g/d, and 1.22 (0.98-1.53) for ≥ 23 g/d in regular drinkers compared with nondrinkers. The HRs for proximal and distal cancer in drinkers vs nondrinkers were 1.69 (1.15-2.47) and 1.24 (0.99-1.55) for ≥ 92 g/d in men, and 1.60 (0.76-3.37) and 1.18 (0.88-1.57) for ≥ 23 g/d in women, respectively. In conclusion, the authors conclude that alcohol intake increased SC risk in men, and heavy drinkers showed a greater point estimate of risk for proximal cancer than for distal cancer.

Song Y. et al. [4] indicate that in their work they have sought to estimate the incidence, mortality, and disability-adjusted life-years (DALYs) of SC at the global, regional, and national levels. SC resulted in 1.3 million (1.2-1.4 million) incident cases, 9.5 hundred thousand (8.7-10.4 hundred thousand) deaths, and 22.2 million (20.3-24.1 million) DALYs in 2019. The age-standardized incidence rate, death rate and DALY rate were 15.6 (14.1-17.2), 11.9 (10.8-12.8), and 268.4 (245.5-290.6) per 100,000 person-years, respectively. Between 1990 and 2019, the global age-standardized incidence rate, death rate, and DALY rate decreased by -30.5% (-36.7 to -22.9), -41.9% (-47.2 to -36.3), and -45.6% (-50.8 to -39.8), respectively. In 2019, most of the global numbers of incidence, death and DALYs were higher among males than females. A considerable burden of SC was attributable to smoking and a high-sodium diet. The largest numbers of incident SC in 2019 were in East Asia (626,488, 95% UI 526,591 to 741,267), high-income Asia Pacific (128,168, 95% UI 108,454 to 147,685) and South Asia (99,399, 95% UI 87,309 to 113,633). The lowest incidence numbers were in Oceania (937, 95% UI 714 to 1186), Australasia (3449, 95% UI 2788 to 4205) and southern sub-Saharan Africa (3610, 95% UI 3282 to 3970). The largest number of deaths due to SC in 2019 were in East Asia (432,991, 95% UI 364,163 to 504,145), South Asia

(99,071, 95% UI 96,309 to 112,441) and high-income Asia Pacific (69,855, 95% UI 59,748 to 75,610). The lowest numbers of deaths were in Oceania (908,693 to 1143), Australasia (2046, 95% UI 1836 to 2224) and southern sub-Saharan Africa (3656, 95% UI 348 to 4009). East Asia (10.1 million, 95% UI 8.5-11.9 million), South Asia (2.8 million, 95% UI 2.4-3.2 million) and high-income Asia Pacific (1.2 million, 95% UI 1.1-1.2 million) had the largest number of DALYs attributed to SC, while these numbers were lowest in Oceania (28,669, 95% UI 21,580 to 36,725), Australasia (38,906, 95% UI 35,984 to 41,627) and southern sub-Saharan Africa (95,721, 95% UI 86,515 to 106,654). In all regions in 2019, the incidences, deaths, and DALYs were higher among males than females. East Asia (30.2, 95% UI 25.5-35.5 per 100,000 person-years), high-income Asia Pacific (28.2, 95% UI 24.2-32.3 per 100,000 person-years) and Andean Latin America (22.4, 95% UI 18.3-27.2 per 100,000 person-years) had the highest age-standardized incidence rates, while high-income North America (6.1, 95% UI 5.4-6.9 per 100,000 person-years), southern sub-Saharan Africa (6.5, 95% UI 5.9-7.1 per 100,000 person-years) and Southeast Asia (6.7, 95% UI 5.9-7.5 per 100,000 person-years) had the lowest rates.

Although the global age-standardized incidence and death rates have decreased, continued growth in absolute numbers in some regions, especially in East Asia, poses a major global public health challenge. To address this, public health responses should be tailored to fit each country's unique situation. Primary and secondary prevention strategies with increased effectiveness are required to reduce the incidence and mortality of SC, particularly in populations with a high disease burden [4].

Trinh T.T.K. et al. [5] conducted a study that aimed to study the patterns of clustering patterns of lifestyle risk factors for SC and examine the association of risk factor clusters with SC screening adherence. Data from the 2019 Korean National Cancer Screening Survey, an annual cross-sectional nationwide survey, were used. The study population included 3539 adults aged 40-74 years with no history of cancer. Six SC risk factors, including smoking, drinking, physical inactivity, obesity, meat intake, and salted food intake, as well as SC screening behaviors, were assessed. The most frequent risk factor for SC was physical inactivity, followed by smoking in males and high salted food intake in females. Compared with participants subjects with no risk factors, those with three or more risk factors were less likely to adhere to screening guidelines (males: adjusted odds ratio [aOR] = 0.35, 95% confidence interval [CI] 0.23-0.53; females: aOR = 0.32, 95% CI 0.21-0.48). As noted by the authors, the findings indicate a disparity in SC screening, such that those with more risk factors are less likely to get screened. Increasing public awareness, providing behavioral counseling, and targeting high-risk populations for screening interventions are critical for promoting cancer screening adherence and reducing the disparity in cancer screening.

A very informative scientific study was conducted by Poorolajal J. et al. [6]. They examined information

on 14 behavioral and nutritional factors that can be addressed in SC prevention programs. PubMed, Web of Science, and Scopus were searched through December 2018. Reference lists were also screened. Observational studies addressing the associations between SC and behavioral factors were analyzed. Between-study heterogeneity was investigated using the χ^2 , τ^2 , and I² statistics. The likelihood of publication bias was explored using the Begg and Egger tests and trim-and-fill analysis. Effect sizes were expressed as odds ratios (ORs) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs) using a random-effects model. Of 52,916 identified studies, 232 (including 33,831,063 participants) were eligible. The OR (95% CI) of factors associated with SC were as follows: *Helicobacter pylori* infection, 2.56 (95% CI, 2.18 to 3.00); current smoking, 1.61 (95% CI, 1.49 to 1.75); former smoking 1.43 (95% CI, 1.29 to 1.59); current drinking, 1.19 (95% CI, 1.10 to 1.29); former drinking, 1.73 (95% CI, 1.17 to 2.56); overweight/obesity, 0.89 (95% CI, 0.74 to 1.08); sufficient physical activity, 0.83 (95% CI, 0.68 to 1.02); consumption of fruits ≥ 3 times/wk, 0.48 (95% CI, 0.37 to 0.63); consumption of vegetables ≥ 3 times/wk, 0.62 (95% CI, 0.49 to 0.79); eating pickled vegetables, 1.28 (95% CI, 1.09 to 1.51); drinking black tea, 1.00 (95% CI, 0.84 to 1.20); drinking green tea, 0.88 (95% CI, 0.80 to 0.97); drinking coffee, 0.99 (95% CI, 0.88 to 1.11); eating fish ≥ 1 time/wk 0.79 (95% CI, 0.61 to 1.03); eating red meat ≥ 4 times/wk 1.31 (95% CI, 0.87 to 1.96), and high salt intake 3.78 (95% CI, 1.74 to 5.44) and 1.34 (95% CI, 0.88 to 2.03), based on two different studies. In conclusion, the researchers note that this meta-analysis provided a clear picture of the behavioral and nutritional factors associated with the development of SC. These results may be utilized for ranking and prioritizing preventable risk factors to implement effective prevention programs.

For example, there are persistent disparities in SC mortality among racial-ethnic groups in the USA, but the extent to which these patterns vary geographically is not well understood. In this paper [7], the following was evaluated age-standardised mortality for five racial-ethnic groups, in 3110 USA counties over 20 years, to describe spatial-temporal variations in SC mortality and disparities between racial-ethnic groups. Redistribution methods for insufficient cause of death codes and validated small area estimation methods were applied to death registration data from the US National Vital Statistics System and population data from the US National Center for Health Statistics to estimate annual SC mortality rates. Estimates were stratified by county and racial-ethnic group (non-Latino and non-Hispanic [NL] American Indian or Alaska Native [AIAN], NL Asian or Pacific Islander [Asian], NL Black [Black], Latino or Hispanic [Latino], and NL White [White]) from 2000 to 2019. Estimates were corrected for misreporting of racial-ethnic group on death certificates using published misclassification ratios. Authors masked (i.e., did not display) estimates for county and racial-ethnic group combinations with a mean annual population of less than 1000; thus, our colleagues report estimates for 3079 (of 3110) counties for the total population, and 474, 667, 1488, 1478, and 3051 counties for

the AIAN, Asian, Black, Latino, and White populations, respectively.

In conclusion, the researchers note that between 2000 and 2019, national age-standardised SC mortality was lowest among the White population in every year. Nationally, SC mortality declined for all racial-ethnic groups across this time period, with the most rapid declines occurring among the Asian (percent decline 48.3% [45.1-51.1]) and Black populations (42.6% [40.2-44.6]). Mortality among the other racial-ethnic groups declined more moderately, decreasing by 36.7% (35.3-38.1), 35.1% (32.2-37.7), and 31.6% (23.9-38.0) among the White, Latino, and AIAN populations, respectively. Similar patterns were observed at the county level, although with wide geographic variation. In 2019, a majority of counties had higher mortality rates among minoritised racial-ethnic populations compared to the White population: 81.1% (377 of 465 counties with unmasked estimates for both racial-ethnic groups) among the AIAN population, 88.2% (1295 of 1469) among the Latino population, 99.4% (663 of 667) among the Asian population, and 99.9% (1484 of 1486) among the Black population. However, the size of these disparities ranged widely across counties, with the largest range from 0.3 to 17.1 among the AIAN population. In interpreting the data obtained, the authors point out that SC mortality has decreased substantially across populations and geographies in the USA. However, disparities in SC mortality among racial-ethnic groups are widespread and have persisted over the last two decades. Local-level data are crucial to understanding the scope of this unequal burden among minoritised groups in the USA [7].

A very interesting paper was presented by Kim D.H. et al. [8]. The authors note that Epstein-Barr virus (EBV)-encoded BamHI-A rightward frame 1 (BARF1) is a putative viral oncogene in EBV-infected SC. The aim of the present study was to investigate BARF1-induced cellular protein and microRNA alterations. In this study, BARF1-expressing SC cells showed a high rate of proliferation, high levels of NFκB, and miR-146a upregulation, which was reversed by NFκB knockdown. During BARF1-induced NFκB upregulation, hCSF1 receptor level was unchanged. Knockdown of BARF1 in the naturally EBV-infected YCCEL1 SC cells suppressed cell proliferation, and downregulated NFκB and miR-146a. SMAD4 was identified as a miR-146a target and was downregulated in BARF1-expressing cells, whereas SMAD4 expression was restored by anti-miR-146a. Knockdown of BARF1 in YCCEL1 cells upregulated SMAD4, and this effect was reversed by miR-146a overexpression. Transfection of BARF1-expressing cells with pCEP4-SMAD4 abolished the cell proliferating effect of BARF1. In SC tissues, miR-146a was expressed at higher levels, and more frequent NFκB nuclear positivity immunohistochemically, but not of SMAD4 nuclear loss was found in the EBV-positive group compared with the EBV-negative group.

In this work, colleagues have demonstrated that EBV-encoded BARF1 promotes cell proliferation in SC by upregulating NFκB and miR-146a and downregulating SMAD4, thereby contributing to EBV-induced

SC progression.

In general, survival for patients with SC is poor. In addition, there is global variation in SC survival [9,10]. Worldwide, with the exception of Japan (69%) and Korea (67%), most areas have an overall 5-year relative survival of SC of about 20%-30%. Japan has had a national endoscopic surveillance program since the early 1970s because of the high SC risk. It is recommended that all people older than 40 years undergo screening with a double-contrast barium X-ray radiography and endoscopy every year. A study in China demonstrated that a preventive intervention which included eradication of *H. pylori*, nutritional supplements, and screening (with double-contrast radiography and endoscopy) resulted in a 49% reduction in relative risk for overall mortality in a high-risk group of individuals [1].

Primary and secondary prevention strategies are the focus of SC prevention. Primary prevention measures involve improvements in environment and lifestyle habits such as tobacco control/smoking cessation, reducing salt intake, increasing fruit and vegetable intake, developing other healthy behaviors (such as Mediterranean diet, higher intake of fiber, physical activity), *H. pylori* eradication, other medications (intake of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, statins), refraining from high alcoholic beverages, sanitation and hygiene improvements. The WHO has set a global goal of reducing the intake of salt to less than 5 g (2000 mg of sodium) per person per day by the year 2025. A meta-analysis of randomized trials (all trials were performed in areas with a high incidence of SC, mostly in Asia), in a total of 6695 participants followed from 4 to 10 years showed that the risk of SC can be reduced by 35% with the treatment of *H. pylori*. In addition to endoscopic and histological surveillance, the American and European guidelines recommend eradication of *H. pylori* in all persons who have atrophy and/or intestinal metaplasia and all persons who are first-degree relatives of SC patients. According to the Asian Pacific Gastric Cancer Consensus, population-based screening and treatment of *H. pylori* infection is recommended in regions which have an annual SC incidence of more than 20/100000. Eradication of *H. pylori* can be achieved with antibiotic therapy; but, the treatment of asymptomatic carriers is not practical as many countries have a very high infection burden (e.g., over 75% of adult persons living in sub-Saharan Africa have *H. pylori* infection) and reinfection is relatively easy [1].

Now, as for this pathology in our country. The incidence of SC in the Republic of Kazakhstan in 2022 was 14.9 (19.9 - men; 10.2 - women) per 100 thousand population with a growth rate compared to the previous year of 11.0% (13.5 - in 2021), which in absolute numbers amounted to 2915 people (2576 cases in 2021), occupying a high 3rd place after breast cancer and lung cancer. The share of cases with a diagnosis established for the first time in their lives, recorded by oncology organizations, was 8.3% (in 2021 - 7.9%), and this is also the 3rd ranking place. At the same time, 1895 men fell ill (specific gravity - 12.5%, 2nd ranking place after lung cancer), women - 1020 [(specific gravity - 5.12%, 6th ranking place after, of course, breast cancer (1st

ranked place), cervical cancer (2nd place), uterine cancer (3rd place), ovarian cancer (4th place) and colon cancer (5th place)] [11].

The incidence of SC was higher than the national average in 9 regions of the country: Kostanay - 22.9 (maximum); Karaganda - 21.5; North Kazakhstan - 21.1; East Kazakhstan - 21.0; Pavlodar - 20.4; Akmola - 20.2; Abay - 19.8; West Kazakhstan - 19.3 and Aktobe - 19.2. The indicator is less than the national average in 10 regions: in Shymkent city - 8.4 (the lowest level); Mangystau - 9.3; Turkestan - 10.3; Zhambyl - 10.4; Almaty city - 12.2; Almaty - 12.6; Atyrau - 13.2; Zhetysu - 13.3; Astana city - 13.5; Kyzylorda - 13.8 regions of the country per 100 thousand population.

The mortality rate from this pathology was 8.0 (men - 10.9; women - 5.24) per 100 thousand population. In the structure of causes of mortality for both sexes in 2022, this pathology ranks high 2nd after lung cancer, amounting to 12.0%, and in absolute numbers - 1560 people. Of these: 1037 are men (specific gravity - 15.1%, 2nd place); 523 - women (specific gravity - 8.5% and high - 3rd ranking place).

The regions where the mortality rate from SC is higher than the national average (8.0 per 100 thousand population) include: Abay - 14.5 (maximum level); Akmola - 12.0; East Kazakhstan and West Kazakhstan - 11.3; North Kazakhstan - 10.2; Pavlodar - 9.9; Karaganda - 8.9; Astana city - 8.8; Aktobe - 8.3. In parity with the republican average level - Kostanay region - 8.0. The lowest rates were noted in Mangystau - 3.9 (minimum level); Shymkent city - 5.5; Kyzylorda - 5.6; Almaty - 6.1; Turkestan - 6.5; Zhetysu - 6.6; Atyrau - 7.3; Almaty city - 7.4 and Zhambyl - 7.7 regions per 100 thousand population [11].

The number of deaths from SC who were not registered with oncology organizations and were diagnosed posthumously in the Republic of Kazakhstan was 35 people; at the same time, the specific gravity was 1.2% and 5th ranking place.

Moreover, during the first year after diagnosis of cancer, every two out of five people die. At the same time, the one-year mortality rate was 40.0%, ranking 5th. The ratio between one-year mortality and neglect (stage IV) was 1.9 in 2022 and this is in 15th ranking place along with cancer of the tongue and oral cavity and malignant bone tumors. At the same time, let us recall that the furthest distance from "1" is the worst ratio between the indicators of one-year mortality and neglect.

It should also be noted that during preventive examinations in 2022, SC can be classified as one of the most actively detected tumors among all cancer localizations (5th rank in terms of the number of identified patients). At the same time, the proportion of cases of SC detected during medical examinations among those newly identified was 55.2% (1574 patients), with a significant increase compared to the level of 2021 (37.1% or 932 people in 2021). Of these, 47.6% (750 patients) were identified in early stages I-II of the disease (in 2021 - 472 patients, which amounted to 50.6%).

The level of morphological verification of SC in the country was 96.1%. At the same time, in 2 regions 100% verification of the diagnosis was provided

(Zhetysu and Mangystau regions); high rates were achieved in Almaty (99.5%), Zhambyl (99.2%), Astana city (98.8%), Abay (98.3%), North Kazakhstan (98.2%), and low - in Kyzylorda (88.5% - the worst result in the country), Almaty city (89.6%), Akmola (93.0%), Atyrau (94.4%), Turkestan (95.3%) regions and Shymkent city (95.9%).

The proportion of patients with early stage I of the pathology under consideration was 6.4% and this is only the 21st ranking among all nosological forms of oncological pathology.

The regions where the proportion of patients with stage I SC is above the national average include the following regions. Two regions are leading by a large margin from other regions: the Kyzylorda region - here every fourth patient with cancer is diagnosed at stage I of the disease (24.8%) and the North Kazakhstan region, where every fifth patient is diagnosed with stage I cancer (20.4%). This is followed by: Zhetysu - 11.8%; Astana city - 11.6%; West Kazakhstan - 9.2%; East Kazakhstan - 7.8%; Karaganda - 7.7%; Almaty city - 7.6%; Mangystau - 7.2% and Pavlodar - 6.7% regions of the republic.

The lowest rates of early diagnosis were stated: in Aktobe - 1.7% (worst result); Turkestan - 1.9%; Shymkent city - 2.1%; Zhambyl - 2.4%; Akmola - 2.5%; Almaty - 2.7%; Abay - 4.2%; Kostanay - 4.3% and Atyrau - 5.6% regions of the country [11].

At the same time, every two out of five patients with SC are detected in the early (I-II) stages of this pathology. The regions where the proportion of patients with SC detected at stages I-II is above the national average (41.4% and only 19th ranking place for this indicator) include the following regions: Atyrau (60.0%); East Kazakhstan (57.4%); North Kazakhstan (56.6%); Pavlodar (53.7%); Kyzylorda (52.2%); Zhetysu (51.6%); Mangystau (50.7%); Turkestan (48.6%); Aktobe (46.6%); Astana city (45.3%); Abay (44.9%) regions.

Low rates of early diagnosis of SC have been established: in the Almaty region (23.2% - the worst indicator); followed by: Shymkent city (24.7%); West Kazakhstan (27.5%); Karaganda (28.1%); Akmola (32.5%); Almaty city (35.2%); Zhambyl (38.4%) and Kostanay (40.3%) regions of our republic [11].

As is clearly seen from the above data across the country, there is a very wide range in early diagnosis indicators, from very good to depressing. Of course, it is necessary to take into account migration processes and other factors influencing early diagnosis rates, but nevertheless, the results speak for themselves.

The specific gravity of stage IV SC among all nosological forms of malignant neoplasms was 21.3%, in other words, every fifth patient is detected in an advanced stage of the disease, and this is the fourth worst indicator in the republic.

As for the average republican indicator of the specific gravity of stage IV, the Karaganda region showed itself on the negative side, where this parameter was 34.7%, followed by West Kazakhstan (31.3%); Akmola (29.9%); Turkestan (27.8%); Kostanay (26.3%); Zhambyl (23.2%) regions and Astana city (22.1%). The

following showed themselves to be the best in this aspect: Mangistau - 4.3%; Kyzylorda - 8.8%; Atyrau – 8.9% and Aktobe – 9.7% of the regions [11].

Statistical data on patients diagnosed with a malignant neoplasm who have been under observation for 5 years or more, and who continue to be observed in 2022, showed that the number of patients under the supervision of oncological organizations in Kazakhstan for more than five years continued to grow and at the end of the reporting year amounted to 110,790 people, with an increase of 6.6% (2021 – 103,935 people, +4.4%) (form No. 7). The specific gravity of this category of patients or five-year survival rate for malignant neoplasms with a growing trend is 55.3% (55.0% in 2021).

We cannot ignore such an important clinical aspect as the coverage in the Republic of Kazakhstan of special treatment for patients diagnosed with SC for the first time in their lives. At the end of 2022, the absolute number of people who completed specialized treatment was 1,019 people, with almost the same number continuing treatment - 1,018 patients. The following results were obtained in percentage terms for methods and types of treatment. Naturally, the most common method of treating SC is complex treatment, which amounted to 49.2%; this is followed by only surgical treatment - 28.3%, only medicinal treatment - 19.3%. Combined radiation and chemo-radiation treatment alone is used extremely rarely (0.5%; 0.3%; 0.3%, respectively).

Further regarding the five-year survival rate of patients. As for SC, at the end of 2022, 6924 people were registered at the dispensary, or 35.5 per 100 thousand population. At the end of 2021 – 6501 patients or 34.0 per 100 thousand population, respectively.

At the same time, the mortality rate of the observed contingents in 2022 decreased compared to the previous year and amounted to 22.5% in 2022 (24.8% in 2021).

The five-year survival rate of patients with SC decreased slightly and amounted to 47.8% in 2022 compared to 48.5 in 2021 [11].

Summarizing the above, we can conclude that stomach cancer occupies a significant place among all existing malignant tumors of other localizations. The variability and veiling of symptoms, its similarity with various non-core processes, leads to neglect of the disease. All this requires both oncologists and, first of all, primary health care workers and, of course, gastroenterologists to increase the level of oncological alertness, inform the population about early symptoms that may indicate this pathology or the onset of proliferative changes and carrying out high-tech diagnostic measures and, as a result, timely treatment. People at risk are advised to regularly visit a gastroenterologist and, if necessary, undergo examination.

An epidemiological assessment of the situation with stomach cancer in our country suggests that there are sometimes significant differences across regions not only in incidence rates, but also in the parameters of early diagnosis and mortality from this pathology. In connection with the above, this pathology continues to be a serious problem in modern clinical oncology.

References:

1. Ilic M., Ilic I. Epidemiology of stomach cancer. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2022 Mar 28;28(12):1187-1203. doi: 10.3748/wjg.v28.i12.1187.
2. Klinicheskij protokol diagnostiki lechenija «Rak zheludka» - Ob#edinennoj komissiej po kachestvu medicinskih uslug Ministerstva zdra-voohranenija Respubliki Kazahstan ot 21 nojabrja 2022 goda, Protokol №174. – 27 s (In Russ.).
3. Tamura T., Wakai K., Lin Y., Tamakoshi A., Utada M., Ozasa K., Sugawara Y., Tsuji I., Ono A., Sawada N., Tsugane S., Ito H., Nagata C., Kitamura T., Naito M., Tanaka K., Shimazu T., Mizoue T., Matsuo K., Inoue M.; Research Group for the Development and Evaluation of Cancer Prevention Strategies in Japan. Alcohol intake and stomach cancer risk in Japan: A pooled analysis of six cohort studies. *Cancer Sci.* 2022 Jan;113(1):261-276. doi: 10.1111/cas.15172.
4. Song Y., Liu X., Cheng W., Li H., Zhang D. The global, regional and national burden of stomach cancer and its attributable risk factors from 1990 to 2019. *Sci Rep.* 2022 Jul 7;12(1):11542. doi: 10.1038/s41598-022-15839-7.
5. Trinh T.T.K., Lee K., Oh J.K., Suh M., Jun J.K., Choi K.S. Cluster of lifestyle risk factors for stomach cancer and screening behaviors among Korean adults. *Sci Rep.* 2023 Oct 16;13(1):17503. doi: 10.1038/s41598-023-44470-3.
6. Poorolajal J., Moradi L., Mohammadi Y., Cheraghi Z., Gohari-Ensaf F. Risk factors for stomach cancer: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Epidemiol Health.* 2020;42:e2020004. doi: 10.4178/epih.e2020004.
7. GBD US Health Disparities Collaborators. The burden of stomach cancer mortality by county, race, and ethnicity in the USA, 2000-2019: a systematic analysis of health disparities. *Lancet Reg Health Am.* 2023 Aug 4;24:100547. doi: 10.1016/j.lana.2023.100547.
8. Kim D.H., Chang M.S., Yoon C.J., Middeldorp J.M., Martinez O.M., Byeon S.J., Rha S.Y., Kim S.H., Kim Y.S., Woo J.H. Epstein-Barr virus BARF1-induced NFκB/miR-146a/SMAD4 alterations in stomach cancer cells. *Oncotarget.* 2016 Dec 13;7(50):82213-82227. doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.10511.
9. Yang L., Ying X., Liu S., Lyu G., Xu Z., Zhang X., Li H., Li Q., Wang N., Ji J. Gastric cancer: Epidemiology, risk factors and prevention strategies. *Chin J Cancer Res.* 2020 Dec 31;32(6):695-704. doi: 10.21147/j.issn.1000-9604.2020.06.03.
10. Balakrishnan M., George R., Sharma A., Graham D.Y. Changing Trends in Stomach Cancer Throughout the World. *Curr Gastroenterol Rep.* 2017 Aug;19(8):36. doi: 10.1007/s11894-017-0575-8.
11. Kaidarova D.R., Shatkovskaya O.V., On-garbayev B.T., Seisenbayeva G.T., Azhmagambetova A.E., Zhylkaidarova A.Zh., Lavrentieva I.K., Sagi M.S. Indicators of the oncology service of the Republic of Kazakhstan, 2022: statistical and analytical materials – Almaty, 2023. – 430 p.